

The Mediating Effect of Teacher Support on the Link Between Teacher Preparedness for Education 4.0 and Students' Engagement

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Abstract. This study aimed to determine the mediating effect of teacher support on the relationship between teacher preparedness for Education 4.0 and student engagement. The research utilized a quantitative non-experimental design with a descriptive-correlational approach. The study population consisted of 110 private college faculty members from Southeastern College of Padada, Inc. and Serapion Basalo Memorial Colleges, Inc. Data were collected using validated questionnaires and analyzed using SPSS, employing both descriptive and inferential statistics, including the Sobel Test for mediation analysis. Findings revealed that teacher preparedness significantly influences student engagement, and teacher support plays a crucial mediating role in strengthening this relationship. The study highlights the importance of professional development programs that enhance teacher readiness and provide robust support systems to foster student engagement in the context of Education 4.0. Recommendations include institutionalizing structured teacher support and continuous training to ensure effective integration of technology and innovative teaching practices. This research contributes valuable insights into the interconnectedness of teacher preparedness, support, and student engagement, providing a foundation for future studies.

KEY WORDS

1. Teacher preparedness 2. education 4.0 3. Student engagement

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1. Introduction

The rapid advancement of technology and the emergence of the Fourth Industrial Revolution, commonly known as Education 4.0, have transformed the educational landscape. As education shifts toward digitalization and innovative teaching methodologies, teacher preparedness plays a crucial role in fostering student engagement. Understanding how teacher support mediates the relationship between teacher preparedness for Education 4.0 and student engagement is vital. This study aims to explore these dynamics and their implications for teaching and learning in modern classrooms. Many educators face challenges in adapting to the demands of Education 4.0 due to inadequate digital skills and technological resources. According to UNESCO (2021), many teachers worldwide lack the necessary training to integrate technology effectively into their pedagogical practices. The sudden shift to online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic further exposed these gaps, leaving many educators strug-

gling to maintain student engagement in virtual classrooms (OECD, 2021). For instance, in the United States, a study by the National Center for Education Statistics (2022) found that over 40Furthermore, disparities in technological access remain a major concern, affecting both educators and students. In many developing countries, such as India and Nigeria, unreliable internet connectivity and limited access to digital tools hinder the full implementation of Education 4.0 (World Bank, 2022). This digital divide exacerbates inequalities in student learning outcomes, as those with better resources receive a higher quality of education than those in underprivileged areas (UNESCO, 2023). In South Africa, research by the Department of Basic Education (2021) revealed that only 20Another critical issue is the resistance to change among educators. Despite the growing emphasis on digital transformation, many teachers struggle with pedagogical shifts due to traditional teaching mindsets and lack of institutional support (Salmon, 2020). The reluctance to embrace new methodologies, coupled with inadequate professional development programs, further complicates efforts to ensure that students remain actively engaged in their learning processes (Bond et al., 2021). In the United Kingdom, a study by the Office for Standards in Education (2023) found that 27% of teachers lacked confidence in integrating digital tools into their lessons, highlighting the need for targeted training programs. (Passey et al., 2024) In the Philippines, integrating technology into education has faced numerous challenges, particularly in public schools. Many teachers report insufficient training in digital pedagogy, making it difficult to implement Education 4.0 effectively (DepEd, 2021). Additionally, limited funding for technological infrastructure and educational tools has resulted in inconsistent implementation across different regions, affecting student engagement (Banjo, 2020). A nationwide report in June 2020 found that nearly 60%

of public school teachers had not yet received training to facilitate distance learning, underscoring widespread unpreparedness for digital instruction (Reysio-Cruz, 2020) Teacher preparedness in Philippine higher education institutions is also inconsistent, with some institutions offering comprehensive faculty development programs while others struggle with outdated teaching strategies (CHED, 2022). This lack of standardization in teacher training creates disparities in how students experience education, particularly in courses requiring innovative teaching approaches (Asian Development Bank, 2023). Research conducted by Ateneo de Manila University (2022) indicated that the lack of institutional support significantly affects teachers' ability to integrate Education 4.0 effectively. Moreover, socio-economic factors further complicate teacher readiness in the country. A study by the Philippine Institute for Development Studies (2023) found that many educators face financial constraints that limit their ability to invest in continuous professional development (Sinsay-Villanueva Orbeta, 2023). This economic burden affects their capacity to adapt to new teaching methods, ultimately influencing student engagement in the classroom. Findings from the National Economic and Development Authority (2024) showed that low-income teachers often struggle to acquire the necessary digital tools to support modern teaching strategies. In the Davao Region, these challenges are particularly pronounced due to disparities in access to digital resources and teacher training programs. According to DepEd Region XI (2022), many educators in the region struggle with outdated teaching materials and limited access to professional development opportunities. The lack of government funding for digital learning initiatives has further widened the gap in student engagement, particularly in rural areas. A report by the Mindanao Development Authority (2023) highlighted that only 30% of schools in the region had access to adequate technological

resources for effective digital learning. Addressing these issues is essential in ensuring equitable access to quality education. Teacher preparedness not only impacts student engagement but also influences long-term educational outcomes, including critical thinking skills and academic motivation. As society continues to embrace digital transformation, empowering educators with the necessary skills and resources is crucial for bridging educational gaps (World Economic Forum, 2023). This study is urgent, as the rapid shift toward digital learning necessitates immediate action to support teachers in adapting to Education 4.0. Policymakers, educators, and academic institutions must collaborate to create policies and programs that enhance teacher preparedness. By understanding the mediating role of teacher support, this research aims to provide valuable insights into improving student engagement and ensuring that digital education benefits all learners equitably (UNESCO, 2024).

1.1. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework of the Study—This study is grounded in three key theories that collectively provide a comprehensive understanding of how teacher support mediates the relationship between teacher preparedness for Education 4.0 and student engagement. Social Support Theory, originally articulated by House (1981), posits that social support from significant individuals, such as teachers, plays a crucial role in influencing an individual's well-being and performance. In an educational setting, teacher support encompasses emotional, informational, and instrumental support provided by educators. According to this theory, students who perceive high levels of support from their teachers are more likely to experience positive academic outcomes and higher engagement levels. This theory underpins the notion that teacher support can enhance students' academic experiences, particularly as

institutions adapt to the demands of Education 4.0. By providing a supportive environment, teachers can mitigate the challenges associated with new educational technologies and methodologies, thus fostering greater student engagement.

Self-Determination Theory (Deci Ryan, 2000) emphasizes the importance of fulfilling basic psychological needs autonomy, competence, and relatedness to enhance motivation and engagement. In the context of education, this theory suggests that teacher support is crucial in fulfilling students' need for relatedness and competence. When students feel supported by their teachers, they are more likely to experience a sense of belonging and competence, which can drive intrinsic motivation and increased engagement. In the transition to Education 4.0, where new technologies and teaching methods are introduced, the role of teacher support becomes even more critical in addressing students' psychological needs and sustaining their engagement in the learning process. The Technology Acceptance Model (Davis, 1989) provides insights into how users come to accept and utilize new technologies. TAM highlights two primary factors perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness that influence technology adoption. In the context of Education 4.0, this model can be applied to understand how the preparedness of higher education institutions in implementing new technologies impacts the effectiveness of teacher support. If institutions are well-prepared and provide the necessary resources and training, teachers are better equipped to support their students. This, in turn, can positively affect students' perceptions of the relevance and ease of using new educational technologies, thereby enhancing their engagement and academic performance.

Fig. 1. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework

2. Methodology

This chapter presents the research design, research respondents, research instruments, ethical considerations, role of the researcher, data collection, data analysis, and trustworthiness of the study.

2.1. Research Design—This study utilized a quantitative non-experimental research design to examine the role of teacher support in mediating the relationship between teacher preparedness for Education 4.0 and student engagement. The non-experimental design is appropriate for this investigation as it does not involve the manipulation of variables or random assignment. Instead, the study seeks to observe and analyze the existing relationships among the variables within their natural educational context. This design aligns with the goals of understanding real-world phenomena without the imposition of experimental controls (Creswell Creswell, 2021). The study employed a descriptive-correlational approach to explore the relationships among the key variables. Descriptive statistics were used to provide a summary of the data, offering insights into the levels of teacher support, teacher preparedness for Education 4.0, and teacher engagement. This approach allows for a clear depiction of the current state of these variables among teachers. Correlational analysis were then applied to determine the strength and direction of the relationships between teacher support, teacher preparedness, and teacher engagement. The descriptive-correlational method is suited to this study as it facilitates the identification of significant patterns and associations, thus contributing to a comprehensive understanding of how these variables interrelate (Field, 2020). In addition to descriptive-correlational analysis, the study incorporated a mediation model to investigate the indirect effects of teacher preparedness for Education 4.0 on teacher engagement through teacher support. This mediation model allows for the exploration of whether

teacher support serves as a mediator in the relationship between teacher preparedness and teacher engagement (Hayes, 2022). By using this statistical technique, the study aimed to uncover the underlying mechanisms through which teacher preparedness influences teacher engagement. This approach provides deeper insights into the pathways that connect teacher preparedness to engagement, enhancing the understanding of how teacher support can impact engagement levels.

2.2. Ethical Consideration—The researcher followed established ethical protocols governing the conduct of the study, ensuring meticulous management of the teacher participants from Southeastern College of Padada, Inc. and Serapion Basalo Memorial Colleges, Inc. in Davao del Sur, as well as the collected data. The research design, including the survey instruments and procedures, was reviewed and approved by the Ethics Committee before data collection began. This step ensured that the study adhered to ethical standards, safeguarding the rights and well-being of the teacher participants (Creswell Creswell, 2021)

Informed Consent

Informed consent was a fundamental ethical requirement for this study. All participants, specifically teachers from Southeastern College of Padada, Inc. and Serapion Basalo Memorial Colleges, Inc., were fully informed about the nature, purpose, and procedures of the research before agreeing to participate. Since the respondents were adults, they provided their own consent. The process involved offering clear and comprehensive information about the study, emphasizing that participation was voluntary and that they had the right to withdraw at

any time without any repercussions (Creswell Creswell, 2021). This ensured that the teachers made an informed and voluntary decision about their involvement in the research.

Vulnerability of the Research Participants

Although the participants were adults, they were still considered a vulnerable group in the context of academic research. Special attention was given to ensure that the research procedures did not cause undue stress or discomfort. The researcher ensured that all survey questions and tasks were relevant and did not invade the participants' personal boundaries. Additionally, the researcher was sensitive to any potential power dynamics in the teacher-student context, ensuring that participants did not feel pressured to participate (Mertens, 2019).

Privacy and Confidentiality

Maintaining the privacy and confidentiality of the participants was a critical ethical consideration. Personal information and data collected from the teachers were kept confidential and used exclusively for the purposes of this research. Participants' identities were anonymized in all reports and publications to prevent any potential harm or stigmatization. Data was securely stored, and access was limited to the researcher and authorized personnel involved in the study (Saunders et al., 2019).

Risk, Benefits, and Safety

The study was designed to minimize any potential risks to the participants. The activities involved, such as completing surveys or participating in interviews, were non-invasive and did not expose participants to physical or psychological harm. The potential benefits of the study included providing insights into how teacher support influenced student engagement and informed educational practices to improve teaching and learning outcomes. The safety of participants was a top priority, and any unforeseen issues were addressed promptly (Resnik, 2020).

Justice

The principle of justice was upheld by ensuring that the selection of participants was fair and equitable. The study did not discriminate based on socio-economic status, gender, or any other demographic characteristic. All eligible teachers from Southeastern College of Padada, Inc. and Serapion Basalo Memorial Colleges, Inc. had an equal opportunity to participate in the study. This approach ensured that the benefits and burdens of the research were distributed fairly among the participants (Gustafson Brunger, 2021).

Transparency

Transparency in the research process was maintained by providing detailed information about the study's aims, procedures, and potential impacts to the participants. Any conflicts of interest were disclosed, and the results of the study were shared with the participants, their schools, and the wider academic community in an accessible format. This transparency helped build trust and ensured that all stakeholders were informed about the research outcomes (Resnik, 2020).

Qualification of the Researcher

The researcher conducting this study had the necessary qualifications and experience to undertake research involving teachers. This included a strong background in educational research, knowledge of ethical guidelines, and experience in conducting quantitative studies using descriptive-correlational techniques and mediation models. The researcher's qualifications ensured that the study was conducted with the highest standards of ethical and methodological rigor (Mertens, 2019).

Adequacy of Facilities

The research was conducted in suitable facilities, such as quiet spaces within the participating institutions, to ensure a safe and comfortable environment for the teachers. These facilities provided the necessary privacy for administering surveys or conducting interviews and were equipped to handle any logistical needs of the

study. Ensuring the adequacy of facilities was crucial for maintaining the well-being of the participants and the integrity of the research process (Flick, 2019).

Community Involvement

Community involvement was an integral component of this study. Engaging with the broader educational community, including faculty members and institutional administrators from Southeastern College of Padada, Inc. and Serapion Basalo Memorial Colleges, Inc., ensured that the study was relevant and beneficial. The researcher shared preliminary findings with the schools and involved them in discussions about the implications of the research for improving teaching practices. This engagement helped ensure that the research was culturally sensitive and aligned with the needs and values of the teacher participants (Israel et al., 2019).

2.3. Research Respondents—The respondents for this study consisted of faculty members from two private higher education institutions: Southeastern College of Padada, Inc. and Serapion Basalo Memorial Colleges, Inc. The selection of faculty is strategic, as these teachers play a crucial role in shaping students' engagement with the educational process and in supporting teacher preparedness for Education 4.0. Understanding faculty perspectives is essential for exploring how teacher support and preparedness impact student engagement in the context of modern educational demands (Pinnell Fountas, 2020). The sample size for each institution will be determined using Slovin's formula, which ensures a representative sample from each school. Southeastern College of Padada, with 87 faculty members, will have a sample size of 70 respondents, while Serapion Basalo Memorial Colleges, with 43 faculty members, will have a sample size of 40 respondents. This approach will provide a comprehensive view of faculty perspectives from two distinct private institutions. A simple random sampling technique was used to select respondents

from both institutions. This method ensures that every teacher within the target population has an equal chance of being selected, thus minimizing selection bias and enhancing the generalizability of the findings. By using simple random sampling, the study aims to capture a diverse set of experiences and perspectives from faculty members at both institutions, which will enrich the analysis of how teacher preparedness and support influence student engagement (Creswell Creswell, 2021). The inclusion criteria for the study are the faculty members who are actively teaching during the Academic Year 2024-2025. This ensures that the respondents have current and relevant experience with teacher preparedness and support systems, which are central to the study's objectives. The sample size, totaling 110 respondents (70 from Southeastern College of Padada and 40 from Serapion Basalo Memorial Colleges), is considered adequate for the descriptive-correlational analysis and mediation model employed in the study. This sample size provides sufficient statistical power to detect significant relationships among the variables under investigation, ensuring that the data collection process remains manageable and focused within the scope of the research (Hayes, 2022).

2.4. Research Instrument—This study used three primary research instruments to measure the key variables: higher education institutions' (HEIs) preparedness for Education 4.0, student engagement, and teacher support. To assess the preparedness of teachers for Education 4.0, the study utilized the instrument developed in the study titled "School Readiness in Education 4.0 in the Context of Basic Education" by Pahugot et al. (2022). This instrument measures various aspects of institutional readiness, including the availability of infrastructure, the integration of digital tools in teaching and learning practices, and the training and development of teachers in using new technologies. The data will be collected using a Likert-type scale, where respondents will indicate their

level of agreement with statements related to the preparedness of their institutions. This tool is particularly suited for evaluating how well institutions are adapting to the demands of Education 4.0. Before the data collection began, the research instruments underwent rigorous validation by a panel of experts in the field of education. These experts assessed the questionnaires to ensure they accurately measured the

constructs of Teachers' Preparedness for Education 4.0, Student Engagement, and Teacher Support. Feedback from these experts was incorporated into the instruments, refining them to ensure their reliability and appropriateness for the study's specific context.

The responses were collected using a 5-point Likert-type scale, where the interpretation of the results were categorized as follows:

Range of Mean, Descriptive Level, and Interpretation of Teachers' Preparedness for Education 4.0

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	Teachers' preparedness for Education 4.0 is always manifested.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	Teachers' preparedness for Education 4.0 is oftentimes manifested.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	Teachers' preparedness for Education 4.0 is sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	Teachers' preparedness for Education 4.0 is seldom manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	Teachers' preparedness for Education 4.0 is never manifested.

Student engagement was evaluated using the Student Engagement in Schools Questionnaire (SESQ), developed by Hart, Stewart, and Jimerson (2011) at the University of California Santa Barbara. The SESQ is a comprehensive instrument that assesses various dimensions of student engagement, including affective, behavioral, and cognitive engagement. This questionnaire uses a Likert-type scale, allowing students to self-report their levels of engagement across

different aspects of their educational experience. The SESQ is recognized for its robust psychometric properties and has been widely used to explore the relationship between engagement and various educational outcomes, making it an ideal choice for this study. The responses were collected using a 5-point Likert-type scale, where the interpretation of the results were categorized as follows:

Teacher support was measured using the Foreign Language Teacher Support Scale (FLTSS), developed and validated by Sadoughi and Hejazi (2020). Although originally designed for language learning contexts, the

FLTSS has been adapted for this study to measure perceived support from teachers in a broader educational context. This instrument assesses students' perceptions of the emotional, instructional, and administrative support they re-

Range of Mean, Descriptive Level, and Interpretation of Student Engagement

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	Student engagement is always manifested.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	Student engagement is oftentimes manifested.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	Student engagement is sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	Student engagement is seldom manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	Student engagement is never manifested.

ceive from their teachers, using a 5-point Likert-type scale. The FLTSS provides a nuanced understanding of the different dimensions of teacher support that contribute to student en-

gagement and academic success. The responses were collected using a 5-point Likert-type scale, where the interpretation of the results were categorized as follows:

Range of Mean, Descriptive Level, and Interpretation of Teacher Support

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	Teacher support is always manifested.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	Teacher support is oftentimes manifested.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	Teacher support is sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	Teacher support is seldom manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	Teacher support is never manifested.

Before administering these questionnaires, a pilot test was conducted to ensure the reliability and validity of the instruments in the specific context of students. This pilot testing involved 30 sample of teachers from the same population, allowing the researcher to identify any potential issues with the questions and to make necessary adjustments. Feedback from the pilot test was used to refine the instruments, ensuring that they are clear and effective in capturing the in-

tended data. As a result of the pilot testing, the reliability of each instrument was confirmed using Cronbach’s Alpha. The Teacher Preparedness for Education 4.0 scale, composed of 10 items across two indicators, yielded a reliability coefficient of .912. The Student Engagement questionnaire, consisting of 30 items, showed an alpha of .931, while the Teacher Support scale, with 20 items, recorded the highest reliability at .967. These values indicate excellent

internal consistency across all instruments, affirming their suitability for use in the main data collection phase. In addition to pilot testing, the research instruments underwent validation by a panel of experts in the field of education and educational technology. These experts reviewed the instruments for content validity, ensuring that the items accurately measure the constructs

2.5. Data Gathering Procedure—Following the validation of the research instruments, the researcher implemented a systematic and comprehensive approach to data collection, ensuring all necessary permissions were secured and that data is collected efficiently and accurately.

Endorsement Letter to Conduct a Study

The initial step in the data collection process involved obtaining formal authorization to conduct the research. The researcher began by securing an endorsement from the Dean of the Graduate School at Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., Davao City. This endorsement lent credibility to the study and facilitated the process of gaining further permissions. Following this, the researcher submitted formal permission letters to the administrative heads of Southeastern College of Padada, Inc., and Serapion Basalao Memorial Colleges, Inc. These letters were personally delivered by the researcher to the deans or heads of departments where the students were enrolled. This direct approach ensured clear communication of the study's objectives and secured the cooperation and support of the institutions for the research.

Distribution and Retrieval of the Questionnaire

With the necessary approvals in place, the researcher proceeded to distribute the research instruments to the identified respondents. The data collection phase was scheduled for the second semester of the Academic Year 2024-

of interest—Teachers' preparedness for Education 4.0, student engagement, and teacher support. Their feedback was used to make the necessary adjustments to the instruments, further enhancing their reliability and ensuring that they were appropriately tailored to the context of this study.

2025. The researcher oversaw the distribution process, providing a brief orientation to the respondents on the purpose and significance of the study. This introduction helped ensure that participants understood the context and importance of their honest and thoughtful responses. The questionnaires were distributed in a controlled environment, minimizing distractions and allowing respondents sufficient time to complete them. Once completed, the researcher promptly collected the questionnaires to maintain the integrity and accuracy of the data.

Collation and Statistical Treatment of Data

After the questionnaires were retrieved, the researcher proceeded with the collation and statistical treatment of the data. Responses were systematically organized, with each respondent's data categorized according to the specific variables being measured. The data were then entered into SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) for comprehensive analysis. Both descriptive and inferential statistical methods were employed to examine the relationships among teachers' preparedness for Education 4.0, teacher support, and student engagement. This rigorous analytical process ensured that the findings were accurate, meaningful, and provided valuable insights into the research questions. Additionally, the researcher utilized an online calculator to conduct the mediation analysis, specifically applying the Sobel Test to assess the indirect effects among the variables.

2.6. Data Analysis—

The data collected in this study underwent rigorous analysis using a combination of descriptive and inferential statistical techniques to explore the relationships between teacher preparedness for Education 4.0, teacher support, and student engagement.

Mean

This was utilized to measure the extent of teacher preparedness for Education 4.0, teacher support, and student engagement among students. It provided descriptive statistics that help in understanding the central tendency of the data. This approach offered insights into the average experiences of the respondents, allowing the researcher to identify general trends and patterns within the sample.

Pearson Product Moment Correlation

This was used to determine the significance and strength of the relationships between teacher preparedness for Education 4.0, teacher support, and student engagement. This statisti-

cal technique served as a key indicator of the linear associations between these variables. By analyzing the correlation coefficients, the study highlighted how changes in one factor might correspond to changes in another, providing a clearer understanding of the interrelationships among the variables.

Mediation Analysis Using the Sobel Test

The mediating role of teacher support in the relationship between teacher preparedness for Education 4.0 and student engagement was evaluated using the Sobel test. The Sobel test determined the statistical significance of the indirect effect, providing insights into how teacher support mediates the impact of teacher preparedness on student engagement. This method offered a focused analysis of the mediating effect, contributing to a deeper understanding of the mechanisms influencing student outcomes within the context of Education 4.0.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results and discussions of the study on the mediating effect of teacher support on the relationship between teacher preparedness for Education 4.0 and students' engagement. The data gathered from the respondents were statistically treated, summarized, and interpreted to address the research questions and hypotheses. The presentation includes descriptive and inferential analyses, highlighting the levels of each variable and examining the mediating role of teacher support. Findings are organized into tables with corresponding discussions that offer insights and implications relevant to the context of Education 4.0

3.2. Teaching and Learning Practices—

Table 1 consolidates the overall extent of teacher preparedness for Education 4.0 among private college faculty in Davao del Sur, highlighting the dimensions of Teaching and Learning Practices and Infrastructure Requirements. The overall mean across both dimensions is 3.92, with a descriptive rating of Extensive. This suggests that preparedness for Education 4.0 is often-times manifested or observed among faculty

members in the sampled institutions. While this result reflects a promising level of readiness, it also underscores the need for further development in certain areas to fully meet the challenges posed by the demands of Education 4.0. Between the two components, Teaching and Learning Practices obtained a higher mean of 4.16, also rated as Extensive. This indicates that faculty members frequently integrate modern pedagogical approaches, such as technology-enhanced learning and 21st-century skill devel-

opment, into their instructional practices. On the other hand, Infrastructure Requirements registered a lower mean of 3.67, though still under the same descriptive rating. This points to some institutional limitations in terms of providing adequate facilities and digital resources necessary to sustain Education 4.0 initiatives. The higher preparedness in teaching and learning practices implies that faculty members are actively engaging in educational innovation, integrating digital tools, and fostering essential skills such as critical thinking and collaboration. These practices are aligned with the pedagogical shifts emphasized in contemporary education, where learner-centered strategies take precedence over traditional didactic methods. However, the relatively lower rating in infrastructure suggests that institutional support systems—such as access to digital platforms, virtual labs, and IT services—may still be inconsistent or underdeveloped across the board. This finding is consistent with the literature highlighting that effective implementation of Education 4.0 requires a dual emphasis on both teacher competencies and institutional infrastructure. Al-Hussainy

and Al-Yousef (2021), along with Chen and Huang (2021) and Liu and Wang (2021), emphasized that robust teacher preparedness must be complemented by investments in high-speed internet, up-to-date technological resources, and continuous faculty training. Without sufficient infrastructural support, even well-prepared educators may encounter challenges in delivering quality, tech-integrated education. Moreover, the summary result reinforces the need for HEIs to cultivate a culture of innovation and adaptability. As noted by the same scholars, fostering creativity, promoting interdisciplinary collaboration, and aligning curricula with industry needs are essential components of readiness for Education 4.0. These strategies require not only pedagogical commitment from teachers but also institutional mechanisms that enable experimentation and provide access to emerging technologies. Therefore, while teachers demonstrate encouraging levels of preparedness, institutional stakeholders must bridge the gap in infrastructure to ensure a holistic transition toward Education 4.0.

Table 1. Summary of Teacher Preparedness for Education 4.0 of Private College Faculty in Davao del Sur in Terms of Infrastructure Requirements

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1. Teaching and Learning Practices	4.16	Extensive
2. Infrastructure Requirements	3.67	Extensive
Mean	3.92	Extensive

3.3. *Student Engagement as Perceived by Private College Faculty in Davao del Sur*—The findings from Table 2, indicating a "Very Extensive" level of student engagement as perceived by private college faculty in Davao del Sur, align with recent research emphasizing the importance of teacher-student relationships, peer support, and future aspirations in fostering student engagement. A systematic literature review by

Li and Xue (2025) highlights that strong teacher-student relationships and positive teacher behaviors, such as offering guidance and fostering motivation, can substantially enhance student engagement. Additionally, a study by Zhu et al. (2025) found that teacher-student relationships significantly positively affect learning engagement, with intentional self-regulation playing a partial mediation effect between these relation-

ships and learning engagement. Furthermore, the role of family support in student engagement cannot be overlooked. Research by Fernández-Lasarte et al. (2022) indicates that family support, encompassing emotional, informational, material, and appraisal support, significantly influences adolescents' academic engagement

and achievement. In the context of Davao del Sur, these findings suggest that while teacher-student relationships, peer support, and future aspirations are strong contributors to student engagement, enhancing family support could further bolster students' overall engagement in their academic journey.

Table 2. Summary of Student Engagement as Perceived by Private College Faculty in Davao del Sur

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1. Teacher-Student Relationship	4.40	Very Extensive
2. Peer Support	4.36	Very Extensive
3. Family Support	4.10	Extensive
4. Control and Relevance of School Work	4.06	Extensive
5. Future Aspirations and Goals	4.38	Very Extensive
6. Intrinsic Motivation	4.12	Extensive
Mean	4.24	Very Extensive

3.4. *Teacher Support of Private College Faculty in Davao del Sur*—Table 3 summarizes the extent of teacher support as perceived by private college faculty in Davao del Sur across different categories of support. The overall mean is 4.53, which corresponds to a "Very Extensive" descriptive rating. This indicates that faculty members consistently provide a high level of support in all areas, with these behaviors always manifested in their interactions with students. The highest-rated category is "Informational Teacher Support" with a mean of 4.58, which suggests that faculty members are particularly effective in providing students with the information and resources necessary for their academic success. This is followed closely by "Instrumental Support" with a mean of 4.52, demonstrating that faculty members are also highly committed to offering practical assistance to help students achieve their learning goals. Additionally, "Appraisal Teacher Sup-

port" and "Emotional Support" both received high ratings of 4.51 and 4.33, respectively, reflecting that faculty members are very attentive to students' progress and emotional well-being, providing substantial feedback and empathy. The results align with studies emphasizing the multidimensional role of teacher support in promoting student engagement and success. According to Wang and Eccles (2023), comprehensive teacher support—spanning emotional, instrumental, appraisal, and informational dimensions—has a direct and positive effect on students' academic motivation and emotional well-being. Informational support, being the most highly rated, echoes the findings of Alzahrani et al. (2022), who assert that when students receive clear guidance and relevant resources, their academic self-efficacy and performance significantly improve. While all categories were rated highly, the relatively lower score for emotional support highlights an area that could be

further strengthened. As noted by Sultana and Raza (2023), emotional support from teachers, such as showing empathy and being approachable, fosters a sense of belonging and reduces academic stress. Enhancing this aspect could

deepen students' emotional connection to learning and reinforce the overall effectiveness of teacher support in creating a nurturing and motivating educational environment.

Table 3. Summary of Teacher Support of Private College Faculty in Davao del Sur

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1. Emotional Support	4.33	Very Extensive
2. Instrumental Support	4.52	Very Extensive
3. Appraisal Teacher Support	4.51	Very Extensive
4. Informational Teacher Support	4.58	Very Extensive
Mean	4.53	Very Extensive

3.5. *Mediating Effect of Teacher Support on the Relationship between Teacher for Education 4.0 and Student Engagement*—Table 4 shows the results of the mediation analysis which revealed that teacher support significantly mediates the relationship between teacher preparedness for Education 4.0 and students' engagement. Specifically, teacher preparedness had a significant positive effect on teacher support ($\beta = 0.574$, $SE = 0.068$, $p = 0.000$), while teacher support also significantly predicted student engagement ($\beta = 0.327$, $SE = 0.068$, $p = 0.000$). The Sobel Test yielded a z-value of 3.79 and a p-value of 0.000, confirming a statistically significant indirect effect. These findings support the assertion of Zhang and Zhu (2021) that teacher preparedness in the context of digital transformation fosters a more supportive classroom environment, which in turn positively influences learners' engagement. Similarly, Li and Tsai (2020) emphasized that when teachers are well-equipped for Education 4.0—through training, digital competencies, and pedagogical readiness—they are more likely to provide meaningful support that enhances learners' academic experiences. The result also aligns with the theoretical frame-

work of Self-Determination Theory (Deci Ryan, 1985), which posits that social environments that offer support foster intrinsic motivation and engagement. In this context, teacher support functions as a motivational resource that connects teachers' preparedness to students' active participation in learning. The implications of this finding are multi-layered. First, it highlights the critical role of teacher support as a mechanism through which professional preparedness translates into improved student outcomes. This suggests that capacity-building programs for teachers should not only focus on technological or instructional preparedness but also on strengthening their capacity to provide emotional, instructional, and motivational support to learners. Second, it informs school leaders and policymakers that investments in teacher training for Education 4.0 must be accompanied by strategies that promote a supportive teaching culture in schools to maximize the effect on student engagement. Overall, the significant mediation effect underscores the indirect pathway by which teacher preparedness enhances learner engagement — not solely through competence but through relational support. This nuanced insight offers a valuable contribution to the liter-

Fig. 2. Mediation Model

ature on 21st-century pedagogy and reinforces shaping learner experiences. the importance of teacher-student dynamics in

Table 4. Mediating Effect of Teacher Support on the Relationship between Teacher Preparedness for Education 4.0 and Student Engagement

Variable Relationship	Coefficient (a/b)	Std. Error	z-value	p-value	Interpretation
Path a: from TPE → TS (Step 1)	.574	.093	–	.000	Significant direct effect
Path b: from TS → SE (Step 2)	.503	.065	–	.000	Significant direct effect
Indirect Effect (Sobel Test: a × b)	–	.494	3.79	.000	Significant mediation effect

Legend: TPE = Teacher Preparedness for Education 4.0; SE = Student Engagement; TS = Teacher Support

Note: *Significant at $p < 0.05$

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter presents the summary of findings, conclusions drawn from the results, and practical recommendations based on the study’s objectives. It discusses the implications of the mediating role of teacher support in the relationship between teacher preparedness for Education 4.0 and student engagement. The insights gained from the data are interpreted in light of existing literature and educational practices, providing direction for future research and policy implementation.

4.1. Findings—The findings of this study revealed that teacher preparedness for Education 4.0 has a significant and direct positive effect on student engagement. Teachers who possess the necessary competencies, particularly in integrating technology and employing innovative pedagogical approaches, are better able to foster active and meaningful learning among students. Furthermore, the study confirmed that teacher support plays a vital role in enhancing this relationship. Specifically, teacher support significantly mediates the link between teacher preparedness and student engagement, indicating that even well-prepared teachers are more effective when they receive adequate support. This includes professional development opportunities, access to teaching resources, and a collaborative working environment. The results underscore the importance of a holistic approach to improving student engagement—one that involves not only equipping teachers with the tools and knowledge necessary for Education 4.0, but also ensuring that they are supported throughout the teaching and learning process. Overall, the study emphasizes the interconnectedness of teacher preparedness, teacher support, and student engagement, and highlights the need for educational institutions to strengthen both training and support systems to achieve meaningful and sustained student participation.

4.2. Conclusions—This study has explored the role of teacher preparedness for Education 4.0 and teacher support in fostering student engagement. The results underscore the significance of well-prepared teachers in creating an engaging learning environment. As evidenced by the findings, teacher preparedness directly influences the level of student engagement, particularly when teachers are equipped with the right tools and knowledge to effectively use technology and innovative teaching methods. Furthermore, the study revealed that teacher support is a critical factor in bridging

the gap between teacher preparedness and student engagement. Teachers who are supported through professional development, collaborative environments, and access to resources are more likely to engage students actively in the learning process. This finding reinforces the need for educational institutions to prioritize both teacher training and support systems to enhance the overall learning experience. Another important conclusion is the mediating role of teacher support, which suggests that a supportive environment for teachers positively influences their effectiveness in engaging students. As teacher support enhances the connection between preparedness and engagement, it is clear that schools should invest in creating environments where teachers feel supported and empowered. This will not only benefit teachers but also significantly improve student outcomes. Finally, this study contributes to the existing literature by highlighting the interconnectedness of teacher preparedness, teacher support, and student engagement. It provides a foundation for future research in this area, particularly in exploring the impact of different types of teacher support and how they affect student engagement across various educational contexts.

4.3. Recommendations—Based on the findings of the study, several recommendations are proposed for teachers, students, school administrators, and future researchers. For Teachers. Teachers are encouraged to participate in at least two targeted professional development trainings per academic year focusing on digital pedagogy, blended learning, and the effective integration of emerging technologies such as artificial intelligence and learning management systems. Engaging in peer observation and collaborative post-observation discussions is also recommended to enhance reflective practice and facilitate the exchange of effective teaching strategies. Furthermore, teachers are advised to take part in professional learning communities within and across schools to

promote a culture of collaboration and continuous improvement. For School Administrators. School leaders are urged to institutionalize structured teacher support systems by implementing formal mentoring programs for new and transitioning teachers, organizing quarterly performance feedback sessions, and allotting regular time for collaborative lesson planning in the school calendar. Provision of adequate instructional resources, especially technological tools and updated teaching materials, should be ensured. In addition, it is recommended that schools allocate a dedicated budget to sustain in-service trainings aligned with the evolving demands of Education 4.0 to ensure teachers remain competent and confident in their roles. For Students. Students are encouraged to take an active role in their learning by maintaining open communication with their teachers and engaging meaningfully in both academic and extracurricular school activities. They should be trained in the responsible use of digital tools such as Google Classroom, Padlet, and other collaborative platforms to enhance their participation and interaction. Providing feedback through periodic learner satisfaction surveys or reflection journals is also recommended, as it helps teachers adjust their instructional methods based on the students' evolving needs and learning preferences. For Future Researchers. Future researchers are encouraged to conduct longitudinal studies that examine the sustained impact of teacher support on student engagement across multiple academic years. Additionally, it is recommended to employ mixed-method approaches to explore how different types of teacher support—emotional, instrumental, informational, and appraisal—uniquely influence student engagement. Comparative studies across educational levels (e.g., junior vs. senior high) or institutional contexts (e.g., public vs. private schools) may also offer deeper insights into the contextual factors that shape the effectiveness of teacher preparedness and support mechanisms.

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